

OIL SPILL RECOVERY

Graphene heaters absorb faster

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Wrapping polymeric sponges in graphene nanoribbons provide an efficient way to separate and absorb heavy crude oil spilled in water.

The majority of the scenarios for the future global energy needs predict that energy demand will triplicate over the 21st century. ^[1] Unless major changes in global governmental policies occur, fossil fuels will preserve their main market share over alternative fuels or renewable energy sources. In this conventional future scenario, the need of extraction of heavy crude oils is expected to increase in order to replace the declining production of medium and light crude oil. ^[2] Due to its consistency, Heavy crude oil is resistant to flow, posing additional extraction and transportation issues with respect to conventional crude oil. Although oil spill incidents continue to decrease after the 1980s, the difficulties faced upon heavy crude oil extraction and transportation, together with the drilling activity in harsh environments like the previously inaccessible areas of Arctic ice melts or the politically unstable geographical areas, could cause new accidental marine oil spills. Furthermore, as the recent history demonstrates, despite the numerous remediation strategies and about 1.84 million gallons of dispersants applied ^[3] during the largest in history Deepwater Horizon oil spill in the Gulf of Mexico in 2010, tar balls continued to wash ashore years after, and thick layers of oil most likely still remain on the seafloor. Therefore, it becomes evident that novel technological solutions for the rapid and efficient remediation of oil spills and especially the ones involving heavy crude oils are essential.

Absorbents with nanotechnology-based engineered surfaces are a realistic way to overcome the limitations of traditional methods used for oil spills cleanup. In most of these novel systems, porous materials are combined with functional nanomaterials for the safe, efficient and fast removal of low and medium viscous oils from water ^[4,5,6], but become much less efficient when applied for the remediation of highly viscous crude oils, mostly due to their considerable low absorption rate. Now writing in Nature Nanotechnology, Ge et al. report on a method to transform a simple polymeric sponge into an efficient sorbent able to rapidly remove highly viscous heavy crude oil spills by wrapping it in graphene nanoribbons. The developed system can rapidly separate from water crude oils of viscosities ranging between 10^3 to 10^5 mPa·s, significantly

higher than the viscosities of oils utilized in most of the nanotechnology based remediation systems (less than 500 mPa·s). This new concept of oil sorbent able to in situ modify and absorb fast highly viscous oils, is based on the combination of a porous material with graphene nanosheets decorating its pores.

Ge et al, combines the graphene's Joule heating properties, and therefore the local temperature increase due to electric current flow, with the heavy crude oil's viscosity dependence on the temperature. The application of a voltage of few tens of Volts and the subsequent current flow through the graphene-wrapped sponge, result in an increase of the sponge's maximum surface temperature up to 350°C. The heat is transferred from the surface of the sponge to the viscous crude oil in its vicinity, decreasing significantly the viscosity of the oil, making possible its subsequent rapid absorption within the porous medium. The warm oil can be absorbed by the sponges then and removed by mechanical squeezing more efficiently than non-heated oil, so it can be efficiently reused for several times. The joule heated sponges can be also used in a continuous flow process.

The speed at which the nanoribbon-wrapped sponges can work is a particularly promising feature. A rapid remediation response in the first hours of the oil spill release is fundamental for the fate of the process. Weathering would further increase the oil's viscosity, would induce emulsification or sedimentation. Dispersants cannot be used above a specific viscosity,^[7] while the skimmers have diverse operation limits in such extreme cases. Most importantly, the increased viscosity would significantly compromise the absorption rate of most of the nanotechnology-based sorbents. As proved by the authors, by applying an electric power density of 0.58W/cm³, the Joule heated sponge obtains an average surface temperature of 148 °C, and can reach its oil sorption saturation 90% faster compared to the non-heated sponge. Under in-situ pumping conditions the oil recovery rate of the Joule heated sponge, when a power of 0.5W/cm³ is applied, becomes 29 times higher compared to the non-heated counterpart with a recovery rate of 2320Kg/h through each Kg of sponge.

Nonetheless, for such a large-scale application, cost effective solutions should be taken into account. One could think that the use of graphene and electric energy would significantly compromise the large-scale applicability of the presented approach. In their detailed study, Yu et al. prove that the centrifuge assisted dip-coating method used in order to wrap the graphene on the pores of the sponge results in the deposition of

just 0.045mg of graphene for each cm³ of melamine sponge. This amount can be further reduced by 50% if the foam is partially coated to the area close to its surface. Furthermore, by concentrating the heating region of the sorbent close to the oil surface, the utilized electric energy can be decreased by 65.6%. Finally, bigger sponges can reduce the heat dissipation by the material's edges, while multiple electrode set-ups can induce a homogeneous heating of larger surfaces and reduced energy consumption.

The original concept of active sorbents able to in-situ modify the crude oil's rheological properties and subsequently remove it, opens up a new era in the rapid removal of viscous oil spills. Following similar strategies, can be envisioned intelligent composites able to remove emulsified viscous oil, as well as extra heavy oils or bitumen from the underwater interface.

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